

VLADIMIR PETROVICH NALIVKIN (1852–1918) IN RUSSIAN TURKESTAN: CAREER, TRANSFORMATION, AND SOCIOPOLITICAL INFLUENCE AT THE TURN OF THE 19TH–20TH CENTURY

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Abstract

This study aims to comprehensively examine the military and civil duties of Russian bureaucrat Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin, who served in Fergana and its surroundings in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, as well as his relations with the local population and his intellectual transformation. Nalivkin's military career began with his participation in the 1873 Hive and 1875 Hokand campaigns, after which he left military service due to conscientious concerns and transitioned to civil-administrative roles. During this period, he learned the local language and culture, taught in Russian-Turkish educational institutions in the region, and contributed to Russification policies through education. Nalivkin's daily observations, memoirs, and works provide an important source for understanding the bureaucratic structure, colonial administration, and socio-political influence of Russia in Turkestan. The study emphasizes that Nalivkin's activities should be evaluated not only as a military strategy but also within the context of socio-political governance and Russian colonial policy in the region. Moreover, his relationships with the local population and his intellectual transformation reveal the limited effects of Russian administration and the processes of social change. In conclusion, this research offers an original perspective on the history of Turkestan during the Tsarist era, the Russian bureaucratic structure, and Russification policies.

Keywords: Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin, Turkestan, Tsarist Russia, Russification, Colonial Administration

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19. YÜZYIL SONU-20. YÜZYIL BAŞI VLADİMİR PETROVIÇ NALİVKİN'İN (1852–1918) KARİYERİ, DÖNÜŞÜMÜ VE TÜRKİSTAN'DAKİ SOSYOPOLİTİK ETKİLERİ

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Öz

Bu çalışma, 19. yüzyıl sonu ve 20. yüzyıl başında Fergana ve çevresinde görev yapmış Rus bürokrat Vladimir Petroviç Nalivkin'in askeri ve sivil görevlerini, bölge halkı ile ilişkilerini ve entelektüel dönüşümünü kapsamlı bir şekilde incelemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Nalivkin'in askerî kariyeri, 1873 Hive ve 1875 Hokand işgallerine katılmasıyla başlamış, ardından vicdani kaygılar nedeniyle askerî görevlerden ayrılarak sivil-idarî görevlere geçmiştir. Bu süreçte, yerel halkın dil ve kültürünü öğrenmiş, bölgedeki Rus-Türk eğitim kurumlarında öğretmenlik yapmış ve eğitim yoluyla Ruslaştırma politikalarına katkıda bulunmuştur. Nalivkin'in günlük gözlemleri, hatıraları ve eserleri, Türkistan'daki bürokratik yapı, kolonyal yönetim ve Rusya'nın sosyal-siyasal etkilerini anlamak açısından önemli bir kaynak sunmaktadır. Çalışma, Nalivkin'in faaliyetlerinin sadece askerî bir strateji değil, aynı zamanda bölgedeki sosyo-politik yönetim ve Rus kolonyal siyaseti bağlamında değerlendirilmesi gerektiğini vurgular. Ayrıca, Nalivkin'in yerel halkla kurduğu ilişkiler ve entelektüel dönüşümü, Rus yönetiminin sınırlı etkilerini ve sosyal değişim süreçlerini ortaya koymaktadır. Sonuç olarak, bu araştırma, Çarlık dönemi Türkistan tarihi, Rus bürokratik yapısı ve Ruslaştırma politikaları üzerine özgün bir bakış açısı sunmaktadır.

Anahtar kelimeler: Vladimir Petroviç Nalivkin, Türkistan, Çarlık Rusyası, Ruslaştırma, Kolonyal Yönetim

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Introduction

Tsarist Russia occupied the Khanate of Kazan in 1552 and the Khanate of Astrakhan in 1556, and subsequently turned its attention to the Kazakh Khanate, bringing it under control in the 19th century. Additionally, the Uzbek Khanates (Khiva, Kokand, and Bukhara) were occupied by Tsarist Russia. Following these occupations, the Russians established military and administrative structures in the region, becoming a significant power in the heart of Turkestan. The local populations in these regions, as with previous invaders, considered the Russians to be merely a temporary force. However, the Russians aimed to ensure the permanence of their presence by establishing military, military-civil, and civil administrations.

This study examines the biography of Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin, who participated in Tsarist Russia's military occupations in Turkestan. It also analyzes Nalivkin's life story and political ideas within the context of the region's social and political transformations. Nalivkin took part in the occupations of Khiva in 1873 and Kokand in 1875 as an officer. These military campaigns, therefore, deeply affected his intellectual and emotional world, ultimately leading to his resignation from military service.

From 1876, when he transitioned into a military-civilian administration role, until his retirement in 1906, Nalivkin held various positions. He served as deputy director of the Namangan region, as a land tax officer and member of the Organizational Commission, and as a representative on special assignments. He was also head of the first Russian-Native School in Tashkent, taught Sart (Chagatai) and Persian languages at the Turkestan Teachers' School, which trained educators, and acted as inspector of public schools in the Syr Darya, Fergana, and Samarkand regions.

In the later years of his life, Nalivkin was also involved in political roles and activities. His political views gradually shifted toward more progressive positions, but his refusal to support either the Bolsheviks or the Mensheviks led to rejection by both factions. Several oppositional factors contributed to his being declared an undesirable figure by the Russian authorities, including his anti-imperialist rhetoric, conflicts with high-ranking officials, incompatibility with the prevailing political climate, and his close relations with the local population.

One of the most striking examples of Nalivkin's closeness to the local population was that he was hidden for months by a Turkic villager while fleeing from the Bolsheviks in fear for his life. His turbulent life, which ended in suicide, together with the gradual evolution of his thoughts and emotions and the critical turning points he

experienced, presents the portrait of an individual who was distinctly different from others of his era.

His Family

Information about Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin's parents is primarily found in his article titled "Moi Vospominaniya o Skobelev." However, the details provided are incomplete and difficult to verify. For instance, while Nalivkin mentions that his maternal grandfather was in Paris in 1814, he does not provide essential information such as his grandfather's name. Furthermore, although he claims that one of his mother's ancestors was among the founders of the military school known as Orlovskiy Kadetskiy Korpus (Nalivkin, 2015: 527), historical records identify Mikhail Petrovich Bakhtin (Shumakov, 2017: 6) as the founder of this institution. Any familial connection between Bakhtin and Nalivkin is not substantiated by available sources. This lack of verifiable basic information thus creates a notable uncertainty.

While providing information about his relatives, Nalivkin states that all of his uncles were soldiers, one of whom died in Sevastopol (Nalivkin, 2015: 527). However, he does not provide details about the number of his uncles, their names, or the circumstances of their deaths. Information about his father is also limited: although he mentions that his father took part in the 1853–1855 Russo-Ottoman War, his name, military rank, and date of death remain unknown. As a child, Nalivkin heard many stories from his father about villages in Ottoman territories, particularly around Kars likely Kuyuryuk-dora (modern-day Kürekdere) and Bash-Kadıklyar (modern-day Başgedikler). These stories left a deep impression on him; during the Russian campaign against Khiva, he reportedly carried his father's Caucasian sword with him (Nalivkin, 2015: 527). Nalivkin's mother taught him how to sew and advised that every officer under his command should learn to take care of their own needs (Nalivkin, 2015: 527–528). Noteworthy details about his mother also include the following: in 1907, after Tsar Nicholas II dissolved the Second State Duma, Nalivkin, then a deputy, did not return to Tashkent to visit his elderly mother, who supported the monarchy. This episode reflects both political differences within his family and how the broader political climate strained personal relationships (Nalivkin, 2015: 527–528). Additionally, official service records indicate that Nalivkin's family belonged to the nobility of Moscow province (Moskovskaya guberniya), although they did not own property (Abashin, 2015: 574).

The reasons behind the obscurities and unknowns in Nalivkin's family background constitute an important question that warrants further investigation. In

this context, it is noteworthy that, while recounting his memories of Skobelev in his memoirs, Nalivkin also refers to his own ancestors. Mikhail Dmitrievich Skobelev and his family were well-known figures in Tsarist Russia, whereas Nalivkin possessed neither widespread fame nor broad public recognition. For this reason, he may have emphasized the military background of his own ancestors to encourage empathy from the reader. By highlighting that his family had participated in Russia's wars, taken on important responsibilities, and that some of his uncles had died in battle, Nalivkin may have sought to reinforce his own identity and position. In doing so, he may have intended readers of his memoirs about Skobelev to perceive him as someone with a comparable military and familial background.

Birth and Education

There are discrepancies among sources regarding Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin's date and place of birth. According to the statements of Nalivkin's daughter, Natalya Vladimirovna, and his daughter-in-law, Natalya Vasilyevna, he was born on July 15, 1855, into a military family (Kotyukova, 2010: 78). In contrast, a Russian source states that he was born in 1852 in Kaluga into a military noble family (Arapov, 2015: 11). An English source, meanwhile, reports that he was born in 1852 in either Kazan or Kaluga as the son of a military officer (Nalivkin-Nalivkina, 2016: 3). In Nalivkin's official service records, his date of birth is listed as February 25, 1852 (Nalivkin, 2015: 524). Although the dates are close, the discrepancies are notable.

Information about Nalivkin's education is not entirely clear. According to an English source, he entered the military preparatory school Pavlovskiy Kadetskiy Korpus in St. Petersburg in 1863, an educational institution designed for young men. In 1872, he graduated from the Pavlovskoye Voennoye Uchilishche, a two-year institute for those who had completed high school or gymnasium. The curriculum primarily focused on topography, cartography, and military law, while natural sciences and languages were also included (Nalivkin-Nalivkina, 2016: 4). Nalivkin's daughter and daughter-in-law state that he began attending the 1st Kadetskiy Korpus in St. Petersburg in 1864 and graduated in 1871. After graduation, he continued at the Pavlovskoye Voennoye Uchilishche and graduated with honors (Kotyukova, 2010: 78). Another source claims that Nalivkin graduated from the 1st Voennaya Gimnaziya and the Pavlovskoye Voennoye Uchilishche in St. Petersburg (Lunin-Miller, 1993: 227). A Russian source notes that he attended the St. Peterburgskiy Voenniy Litsey and, after graduating, was admitted to the Pavlovskoye Voennoye Uchilishche as one of the most talented students in his class (Abashin, 2015: 22).

In general, although there are minor discrepancies in exact dates across different sources, there is a consensus that Nalivkin received his initial military training in St. Petersburg and subsequently attended the Pavlovskoye Voennoye Uchilishche. His graduation is dated either 1872 or 1873, after which he began his service in Turkestan (Kotyukova, 2010: 78; Arapov, 2015: 11; Abashin, 2015: 22; Nalivkin-Nalivkina, 2016: 2). According to official service records, Nalivkin first enrolled at the 1st St. Peterburgskaya Voyennaya Gimnaziya on August 1, 1870, and later completed a course in the natural sciences at the Pavlovskoye Voennoye Uchilishche, graduating with first-class honors. The records also indicate that he entered into service on August 1, 1870, selected from among the students of the St. Peterburgskaya Voyennaya Gimnaziya (Abashin, 2015: 575).

In his recollections involving General Skobelev, Nalivkin notes that during his time at military school, he had the opportunity to join the Izmailovskiy Guards Regiment but declined due to financial constraints. He suggests, however, that the underlying reason was his desire to engage in active combat, which led him to join the Orenburg Cossack Army stationed in Tashkent (Nalivkin, 2015: 528). This choice indicates that Nalivkin may have been influenced by the attitudes of his elders and by contemporary perceptions of military service among men of his time. Moreover, it marked a significant turning point in his career. Although it is impossible to know how his career might have developed had he joined the Izmailovskiy Guards, this remains a compelling subject for reflection.

Military Career

Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin's military career unfolded alongside the Russian Empire's campaign to occupy Turkestan. His first assignment was participation in the 1873 Khiva Campaign under Russian General Mikhail Skobelev (1843–1882). He later took part in the Battle of Göktepe against the Turkmen and the 1875–1876 campaign in Kokand (Kotyukova, 2010: 78). In his memoirs concerning Skobelev, Nalivkin recalls that in 1875, just after his recent marriage and prior to departing for the Kokand campaign, his mother encouraged him to devote himself to military service (Nalivkin, 2015: 528). He notes that he promised her he would not be a coward. According to his own writings, a major turning point in his military career occurred during the Battle of Geok-Tepe, where he witnessed the massacre of unarmed civilians by Russian troops encountering not enemy soldiers but men, women, and children (Nalivkin, 2015: 536–538). This experience profoundly disturbed him and led to the realization that he could no longer continue as a soldier. He felt compelled to escape in order to preserve his

conscience (Nalivkin, 2015: 543). His distress and psychological fatigue during this period are evident from records dated July 1875. Around this time, he traveled to Saratov for a vacation, where he married Maria Vladimirovna Sartory. Their marriage was officially registered on September 8, 1875 (Nalivkin, 2015: 543).

While in Saratov, Nalivkin learned that the Tashkent forces were preparing to launch their campaign against Kokand. Without completing his vacation, he returned to Tashkent in September and joined the Namangan detachment in November. Even in Namangan, he felt overwhelmed and disillusioned (Nalivkin, 2015: 531, 532; Kotyukova, 2010: 78, 80). In 1876, he prepared a medical report regarding his health condition and initiated discussions to transition into a military-civil administration role (Nalivkin, 2015: 544). On January 26, 1876, General Skobelev appointed Nalivkin as Deputy Head of the Namangan District. He held this position for two years and also worked for a period on a land surveying and regulation commission (Nalivkin, 2015: 544, 545, 548). However, Nalivkin did not find satisfaction in this new role either. On May 29, 1878, he resigned from his post, officially citing health reasons (Abashin, 2015: 22, 23; Kotyukova, 2010: 76). In explaining his resignation, Nalivkin pointed to his inability to communicate effectively with the people of Namangan due to the language barrier, as well as to material shortages that hindered his work. He also expressed criticism of Russian administrators, accusing them of failing to understand the region and its people a level of ignorance he believed would ultimately cost lives (Nalivkin, 2015: 542, 543, 548, 549). The military career Nalivkin had once dreamed of was short-lived, ultimately causing him emotional distress and moral conflict. These experiences led to his departure from military service. The shortcomings he later observed in the military-civil administration also contributed to his decision to resign from that role.

According to his official service record, Nalivkin was promoted to the rank of Junker (officer cadet) on August 29, 1871, and advanced to Senior Sergeant on November 13, 1871. On July 17, 1872, he was commissioned as a Lieutenant in the Horse Artillery Brigade of the Orenburg Cossack Army. Due to his military achievements, he was promoted to Captain on January 18, 1874. On January 27, 1876, he was appointed Acting Deputy Head of the Namangan District Branch, and later, on October 6, 1876, he was assigned to the Kokand Organizational Commission. He officially retired from military service on May 29, 1878, with the rank of Staff Captain, citing health reasons (Abashin, 2015: 575). Nalivkin participated in the Khiva Campaign from March 14 to October 13, 1873. Following his retirement, he remained officially listed as retired from May 29, 1878, until September 23, 1884 (Abashin, 2015: 577-578).

Post-Military Career

After resigning from his military post in 1878, Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin lived for a time with his family in the Radvan region among the Kipchak people. Later that year, he settled in the village of Nanay in the Fergana Valley, purchasing a courtyard house and a small plot of land. Between 1878 and 1884, Nalivkin and his wife, Maria, lived in Nanay. During this period, they both learned the local language, adopted regional agricultural practices, and engaged in farming while closely observing the lifestyle of the local population (Kotyukova, 2010: 76; Kotyukova, 2016: 62; Arapov, 2015: 12-13; Nalivkin-Nalivkina, 2016: 1-2, 3, 6-7). Despite his critical views on military service, records indicate that Nalivkin registered as a military reservist upon his resignation. While sources do not provide a clear explanation for this decision, it may have been motivated by the need to ensure his family's financial security or by social and emotional pressures of the time. In 1884, Nalivkin was reassigned to a new administrative post in Kokand as part of the Russian imperial administration in Turkestan (Kotyukova, 2010: 76; Kotyukova, 2016: 62; Nalivkin-Nalivkina, 2016: 3). That same year, he was transferred to Tashkent to serve under Po Ustroystvu Bitu Tuzemchev, where he came to the attention of General N. O. von Rosenbach, who offered him support. As part of Rosenbach's Russian-Native Schools project, actively launched during his tenure from 1884 to 1889, Nalivkin was appointed the first teacher at the Russian-Native School established in Tashkent in 1884. He later served as an instructor of Turkestani languages at the Turkestan Teachers' Seminary. His work in education continued until 1890, when he was appointed Inspector of Public Schools (Abashin, 2015: 22-23; Arapov, 2015: 13). The primary aim of the Russian-Native Schools in Tashkent was to teach Russian to the children of the local population and to prepare them to serve as translators or mid-level clerks in the Russian colonial administration. In this context, Nalivkin authored a textbook in 1885 titled *Azbuka Dlya Russko-Muslim'manskikh Shkol Osedlogo Naseleniya Turkestanskogo Kraya* (*An Alphabet for Russian-Muslim Schools Among the Settled Population in the Turkestan Region*), designed to facilitate the acquisition of Russian by native children. In 1886, he published *Kratkaya Istoriya Kokandskogo Khanstva* (*A Concise History of the Kokand Khanate*). That same year, together with his wife Maria Nalivkina, he co-authored an ethnographic study titled *Ocherk Bitu Jenshinu Osedlogo Tuzemnogo Naseleniya Fergani* (*An Essay on the Lifestyle of the Settled Indigenous Population in the Fergana Valley*), documenting their observations of the everyday lives of Muslim women in Fergana (Abashin, 2015: 580).

In 1890, Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin was appointed Third State Schools Inspector, responsible for overseeing Muslim schools in the Turkestan region. He appears to have served in this role until 1895 or 1896 (Muhammedov, 2017: 110, 120-

123; Kotyukova, 2010: 76; Arapov, 2015: 13; Abashin, 2015: 43; Lunin-Miller, 1993: 227). His relocation to Samarkand in 1896 is attributed to a personal conflict with F. M. Kerensky, then Chief Inspector of the Third State Schools District (Arapov, 2015: 14; Kotyukova, 2015: 67, 69-83; Kotyukova, 2010: 80). Between 1896 and 1899, Nalivkin served as one of three inspectors for state schools in the Samarkand region. His responsibilities covered both local (Muslim) and Russian schools, allowing him to contribute directly to the multicultural structure of the region's educational policies (Muhammedov, 2017: 117, 131). In 1899, drawing upon his knowledge of local languages, Islamic law, and Muslim communities, Nalivkin was appointed by the Governor-General of Turkestan as a senior official assigned to special duties. From 1899 to 1901, he served as senior assistant for special affairs under the Governor-General of Turkestan (Abashin, 2015: 47; Arapov, 2015: 13; Lunin-Miller, 1993: 227). A major factor in this appointment was the Andijan Uprising of 1898, which occurred in the Syr Darya, Fergana, and Samarkand regions. As an expert familiar with the region and its people, Nalivkin was expected to contribute to the administration's policy response to the rebellion. Following the uprising, his views appear to have shifted toward justifying Russian imperial authority and advocating for an increased military presence in the region (Nalivkin, 1913: 135-136; Arapov, 2015: 13; Abashin, 2015: 47-48, 57; Muhammedov, 2017: 124).

Between 1901 and 1904, Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin served as assistant to the military governor of the Fergana region. He was initially appointed deputy to Governor A. P. Chaikovsky on March 27, 1901. However, when Chaikovsky was reassigned in May of the same year, Lieutenant General Grigory Alekseyevich Arendarenko replaced him (Arapov, 2015: 13-14; Abashin, 2015: 24). Following a series of administrative disagreements with Arendarenko, Nalivkin was recalled to Tashkent, where he participated in various administrative commissions.

In 1905, Nalivkin began writing his work *Natives Tuzemtsı Ranshe i Teper (The Natives Then and Now)*, which was published in 1913. This project was initiated at the request of the Governor-General of Turkestan, N. N. Tevyashev, who asked Nalivkin to provide written and oral assessments of the socio-cultural transformations in the region before and after the Russian conquest. Believing that this topic would attract wider public interest beyond administrative authorities, Nalivkin systematically compiled his personal observations and evaluations (Abashin, 2015: 41; Kotyukova, 2015: 64; Kotyukova, 2010: 78, 80). In 1906, while serving under Governor-General D. L. Subbotich, Nalivkin resigned from his position, citing "family reasons." Upon his resignation, he was awarded the civil rank and the honorary title of "Actual State Councilor" (Nalivkin, 1913: 3). However, since he had not completed the required 25

years of active service, his retirement pension was calculated at only half of his salary 1,125 rubles. In 1907, following the publication of his memoirs about General Skobelev, half of this pension was further revoked. Some sources suggest that this deduction was politically motivated due to Nalivkin's opposition to the regime (Kotyukova, 2010: 79; Arapov, 2015: 14; Abashin, 2015: 25-26). After retirement, Nalivkin continued his intellectual pursuits by teaching courses in Islamic law and the Sart language (Chagatai Turkic). Additionally, he collaborated with *Russkiy Turkestan*, a contemporary legal socialist (Social Democrat) publication, thereby maintaining an active role in the intellectual life of the region (Kotyukova, 2015: 146, 147-148; Arapov, 2015: 14; Kotyukova, 2015: 96).

Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin's post-military public service career can be traced in detail through official state records. On July 27, 1884, he was appointed as a junior official assigned to special duties under the Military Governorship of the Fergana region. Subsequently, on September 23, 1884, he was assigned to the military-civil administration of the Turkestan Governor-Generalship, before being reassigned on October 18, 1884, once again to special duties under the Fergana Military Governorship. On January 1, 1885, at his own request, he was relieved from this position and transferred to the service of the Turkestan Governor-Generalship. On January 10, 1885, Nalivkin was tasked with overseeing and maintaining the Russian-Turk school in Tashkent (Abashin, 2015: 575).

On the same date, in addition to his primary duties, he was permitted to serve as a salaried instructor of local dialects at the Turkestan Teachers' School. On February 7, 1885, Nalivkin was removed from the military-civil service staff of the Turkestan Governor-Generalship and officially appointed as a local dialects teacher at the Turkestan Teachers' School. His expertise extended beyond education into administrative translation work. On September 6, 1886, he was appointed chairman of the commission responsible for translating the Regulation on the Administration of the Turkestan Region into the Sart language. Following this, on December 24, 1886, Nalivkin was assigned for two months to inspect both existing and newly established Russian schools in the Syr Darya and Fergana regions. Similarly, on April 1, 1888, he was appointed for one month to supervise Russian schools in Fergana and Samarkand. His translation skills were further utilized when, on August 23, 1888, he was appointed chairman of the commission tasked with translating administrative irrigation directives in the Turkestan province into the Sart language (Abashin, 2015: 575-576).

Nalivkin's ascent within the administrative hierarchy continued with his appointment on July 27, 1890, as the Third Inspector of Schools in the Turkestan region. Parallel to this position, he was promoted to Senior Council Member on January 1, 1889,

and later to Member of the State Council on January 1, 1897. On May 2, 1899, Nalivkin was appointed as a senior official assigned to special duties under the Governor-General of Turkestan (Abashin, 2015: 576). Shortly thereafter, on May 14, 1899, he was additionally appointed Honorary Justice of the Peace at the Tashkent District Court. One of the highest positions he held during his administrative career was his appointment on March 28, 1901, as Deputy to the Military Governor of the Fergana Province, filling a previously vacant post; the appointment officially took effect on March 27, 1901. Subsequently, on November 28, 1904, he was reassigned to the Turkestan Governor-Generalship by decree, within the civilian ranks of the military administration, in one of the highest-ranking administrative positions. Nalivkin was not only involved in administration but also engaged in structural reforms. On January 21, 1905, he was appointed as a member of a commission responsible for overseeing all economic activities of the Tashkent Municipal Government. Later that year, on November 21, 1905, he was appointed to a commission tasked with reviewing existing legislation in the Transcaspian region and formulating its integration into the administrative framework of the Turkestan region (Abashin, 2015: 576, 577).

Political Career

In 1907, Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin was elected to the Second State Duma as the deputy representing Tashkent, thus becoming a political voice for Russian Turkestan. Upon entering politics, Nalivkin increasingly aligned himself with socialist ideologies and began to openly express his anti-monarchist views. In his speeches in the Duma, he strongly criticized the judicial system and policies of Tsarist Russia, adopting an openly oppositional stance (Kotyukova, 2010: 76; Arapov, 2015: 14; Lunin-Miller, 1993: 227). Following the dissolution of the Second Duma in the same year, he returned to Tashkent (Arapov, 2015: 14; Abashin, 2015: 26; Kotyukova, 2010: 81). Nalivkin not only held these political views personally but also attempted to persuade those around him to adopt them. He expected ideological conformity from both his family members and close friends and reportedly cut ties with those who disagreed—including his own mother. During this period, Nalivkin's social circle increasingly consisted of local intellectuals and individuals with socialist leanings, reflecting his shift away from imperial administrative circles toward a more activist, oppositional community (Kotyukova, 2010: 81–82, 84; Abashin, 2015: 26).

Between 1907 and 1917, Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin held no official governmental position and supported himself through writing and publishing (Abashin, 2015: 26; Kotyukova, 2010: 77; Kanlıdere, 2020: 477). During this period, he

authored several works and contributed articles to various newspapers. Following the February Revolution of 1917, Nalivkin became actively involved in the political transformation of Turkestan. In March 1917, he was appointed editor of the newspaper *Turkestanskije Vedomosti* (*Turkestan Gazette*) and took over the administration of *Nejat*, formerly known as *Turkestanskaya Tuzemnaya Gazeta* (*The Turkestan Indigenous Gazette*) (Abashin, 2015: 26). After the revolution, the last Tsarist Governor, General of Turkestan, General A. N. Kuropatkin, a former acquaintance of Nalivkin, was removed from office. Between the February and October Revolutions of 1917, Nalivkin assumed key roles in several regional governing bodies. On July 19, 1917, he was elected Chairman of the Turkestan Committee upon the recommendation of the Soviets and by decision of Russian Prime Minister Alexander Kerensky, officially assuming the post on July 28. In September 1917, he was appointed Chairman of the Provisional Government's Turkestan Committee, further solidifying his role in the rapidly shifting political landscape of the region (Abashin, 2015: 27; Kotyukova, 2010: 79; Arapov, 2015: 15; Lunin-Miller, 1993: 228; Togan, 2020: 131).

In his various roles during the revolutionary period, Nalivkin sought to mediate between opposing factions, assuming the role of a conciliator rather than a partisan (Abashin, 2015: 27; Togan, 2020: 139). His faith in the revolution was rooted not in violence but in dialogue and mutual understanding (Lunin-Miller, 1993: 227-228). This approach reveals a significant evolution in his political thought, particularly compared to the stance he had taken during the Russian occupation of Central Asia between 1898 and 1901. Intellectually, Nalivkin displayed a complex and sometimes contradictory positions at times supporting the occupation, at other times advocating for the autonomy of local populations. This ambivalence led to divided opinions among intellectuals in the Turkic world: while some regarded him as a friend and ally, others viewed him as inconsistent and unreliable (Lunin-Miller, 1993: 227; Togan, 2020: 114, 115, 135, 152, 153). Nalivkin believed that Russian intellectuals should adopt a modest lifestyle and integrate themselves into the daily lives of the people. He was convinced that by doing so, they could help improve the living conditions of peasants and lay the groundwork for meaningful social transformation. During World War I in 1914, Nalivkin publicly stated that the war was not in the best interest of the Russian people. Later, during the Central Asian Uprising of 1916 in Russian Turkestan, he once again chose dialogue over repression, attempting to persuade the insurgents through conversation rather than force (Kotyukova, 2010: 86).

However, on September 12, the Bolsheviks declared that power had been transferred to the Soviets and announced the formation of a Revolutionary Committee. Nalivkin regarded this move as an uprising rather than a legitimate transfer of

authority. In response, he appealed to Provisional Government leader Alexander Kerensky, requesting that military forces be dispatched to suppress the revolt. He also promised to keep Kerensky informed about the conflict between the Turkestan Committee and the insurgents. His failure to deliver this promised report, however, drew heavy criticism. Shortly thereafter, a punitive expedition was launched against Tashkent, and Nalivkin was dismissed from his position as Chairman of the Provisional Government's Turkestan Committee (Abashin, 2015: 27-28; Kotyukova, 2010: 77; Lunin-Miller, 1993: 228). During this period, Nalivkin found himself increasingly isolated, even by former friends who had come to support either the Bolsheviks or the Mensheviks. His political marginalization was largely due to the perception that his ideological stance had shifted too far to the radical left, alienating allies across the political spectrum (Togan, 2020: 152, 153; Abashin, 2015: 50-52; Kotyukova, 2010: 82).

Death

After being dismissed from his government position by the Bolsheviks in 1917, Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin was forced to flee his home and go into hiding between October 1917 and January 1918. During this time, concerned that Bolsheviks named Tabolin and Kolesov were pursuing him and that his life was in danger, he hid for a while in the garden of a local Turk. Because of this hiding period, he was unable to attend the funeral of his wife Maria, who died in November 1917 (Lunin-Miller, 1993: 228; Nalivkin-Nalivkina, 2016: 8; Togan, 2020: 140, 163; Kotyukova, 2010: 79; Abashin, 2015: 28). On January 20, 1918, Nalivkin visited Maria's grave in Tashkent and committed suicide with his own pistol at 9 a.m. In his suicide note, which he had placed in a soldier's cap he was wearing, he stated that he "blamed no one for his death" and wrote: "I do not agree with what is being done, but I do not want to be an enemy of the people, and therefore I am leaving life." He requested that his funeral be conducted in a "modest, proletarian, and civilized" manner. He also emphasized that he had not followed any religious beliefs for a long time and asked for a secular ceremony (Arapov, 2015: 15; Abashin, 2015: 28; Kotyukova, 2010: 79-80; Lunin-Miller, 1993: 228). The graves of Nalivkin and his wife Maria at the old Russian Cemetery in Tashkent have not survived. The crosses on their tombstones were removed in 1920, and the graves were destroyed in 1942.

Conclusion

Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin, though initially pursuing a military career in line with his family's expectations, underwent a profound personal transformation after confronting the harsh realities of war. Witnessing the killing of civilians during the Khiva and Kokand campaigns brought his moral concerns to the forefront, prompting him to resign from military service and turn toward civil-administrative duties. These experiences revealed the Russian authorities' limited understanding of local populations and exposed systemic deficiencies in colonial governance, compelling Nalivkin to navigate persistent ethical dilemmas that deeply shaped his administrative approach.

During his civil service in Fergana, Tashkent, and Samarkand, Nalivkin actively engaged with local communities, striving to learn their language and culture. Relocating with his family to rural areas allowed him to observe everyday life firsthand, experiences that informed his work on Russo-native schools and educational reforms. His efforts to translate administrative regulations into local languages, supervise schools, and balance the needs of Russian authorities with those of indigenous populations demonstrate that his activities extended beyond bureaucratic duties, reflecting a broader engagement with the region's socio-political dynamics. In this respect, Nalivkin can be considered an early example of a mediatory figure within the Russian colonial administration, seeking to bridge imperial authority and local society.

During the 1917 Revolution, Nalivkin's expertise and mediating skills were recognized by both local authorities and the Russian Provisional Government. Nevertheless, he maintained independence, guided by his own ethical principles. Despite his empathy toward local communities and support for limited autonomy, his Eurocentric perspective on education, religion, and social customs highlighted the tension between genuine concern for locals and the constraints of colonial governance. This tension underscores Nalivkin's paradoxical position as both a reformer and a bureaucrat limited by the intellectual and institutional boundaries of his time.

Nalivkin's life was marked by his wife's death, professional conflicts, and increasing social isolation, ultimately culminating in his tragic suicide. Existing sources, including official reports, published works and administrative records, offer valuable insights into his career, intellectual development and the socio-political fabric of Russian Turkestan. Yet the perspectives of local intellectuals and evaluations by contemporaneous Russian officials with differing views remain scarce. These gaps highlight the need for further comparative and interdisciplinary research to fully understand Nalivkin's contributions, motivations, and long-term impact on the region.

Bibliography

- Abashin, S. N. (2015). Poslujnoy Spisok Sostoyashego v Rasporyajenii Turkestanskogo General-Gubernatora Deystvitel'nogo Statskogo Sovetnika Vladimira Petrovicha Nalivkina [Service Record of Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin, Actual State Councilor, in the Office of the Governor-General of Turkestan]. S. N. Abashin vd. (Ed.) *Polveka v Turkestane V. P. Nalivkin: Biografiya, Dokumenti, Trudi* [V. P. Nalivkin in Turkestan: Half a Century of Life, Documents, and Works]: In 574-578. Moskva: İzdatel'skii Dom Mardjani.
- Abashin, S. N. (2015). Spisok Pechatnih Rapot Vladimira Petrovicha Nalivkina [Catalog of Printed Reports by Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin]. S. N. Abashin vd. (Ed.) *polveka v Turkestane V. P. Nalivkin: Biografiya, Dokumenti, Trudi* [V. P. Nalivkin in Turkestan: Half a Century of Life, Documents, and Works]: In 579-585. Moskva: İzdatel'skii Dom Mardjani.
- Abashin, S. N. (2015). V. P. Nalivkin: Budet to, Chto Neizbejno Bit'; i to, Chto Neizbejno Doljno Bit', Uje ne Mojet ne Bit' [V. P. Nalivkin: What Is Inevitable Will Happen; What Must Inevitably Be Can No Longer Not Be]. S. N. Abashin vd. (Ed.) *Polveka v Turkestane V. P. Nalivkin: Biografiya, Dokumenti, Trudi* [V. P. Nalivkin in Turkestan: Half a Century of Life, Documents, and Works]: In 64-131. Moskva: İzdatel'skii Dom Mardjani.
- Arapov, D. Yu. (2015). Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin (Biograficheskaya Spravka) [Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin: A Biographical Note]. S. N. Abashin vd. (Ed.) *Polveka v Turkestane V. P. Nalivkin: Biografiya, Dokumenti, Trudi* [V. P. Nalivkin in Turkestan: Half a Century of Life, Documents, and Works]: In 11-16. Moskva: İzdatel'skii Dom Mardjani.
- Kanlıdere, Ahmet. (2020). İdil-Ural ve Orta Asya'da Kültürel ve Toplumsal Dönüşüm (1800-1991), Ahmet Kanlıdere-İlyas Kemaloğlu (Ed.) *Ötüken'den Kırım'a Türk Dünyası Kültür Tarihi: In 445-496*. İstanbul: Ötüken.
- Kotyukova, Tatyana V. (2015). Antipod Cheloveka v Futlyare Vosspotinaniya o Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin [The Antipode of Man in a Case: Reflections on Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin]. S. N. Abashin vd. (Ed.) *Polveka v Turkestane V. P. Nalivkin: Biografiya, Dokumenti, Trudi* [V. P. Nalivkin in Turkestan: Half a Century of Life, Documents, and Works]: In 146-163. Moskva: İzdatel'skii Dom Mardjani.
- Kotyukova, Tatyana V. (2015). Povest o Tom, Kak Possopilsya Vladimir Petrovich s Fedorom Mihailovichem i s Georgiyem Aleksiyevidchem [The Story of How Vladimir Petrovich Quarreled with Fyodor Mikhailovich and Georgiy Alekseyevich]. S. N. Abashin vd. (Ed.) *Polveka v Turkestane V. P. Nalivkin: Biografiya, Dokumenti, Trudi* [V. P. Nalivkin in Turkestan: Half a Century of Life, Documents, and Works]: In 64-131. Moskva: İzdatel'skii Dom Mardjani.
- Kotyukova, Tatyana V. (2010). Antipod Cheloveka v Futlyare Vosspotinaniya o Vladimir Petroviche Nalivkine [The Antipode of Man in a Case: Memoirs on Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin]. *Vostochny Arhiv* [The Eastern Archive] (e-journal), 2010 (21): <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/antipod-cheloveka-v-futlyare-vospominaniya-o-v-p-nalivkine/viewer>, Access date: (30.07.2025).
- Kotyukova, Tatyana V. (2016). Ocherk Bita Jenshini Osedlogo Tuzemnogo Naseleniya Fergani V. P. i M. V. Nalivkinih [Study on the Life of the Sedentary Indigenous Population of V. P. i M. V. Nalivkinih]

- Fergana by V. P. and M. V. Nalivkin]. *Vostochniy Arhiv [The Eastern Archive]*, (e-journal), 2016 (33):
<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ocherk-byta-zhenschiny-osedlogo-tuzemnogo-naseleniya-fergany-v-p-i-m-v-nalivkinyh-neopublikovannye-retsensii/viewer>, Access date: (30.07.2025).
- Lunin, B. V.-Miller, V. I. (1993). Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin. P. V. Volobuyev [Vladimir Petrovich Nalivkin, by P. V. Volobuyev]. (Ed.) *Politicheskiye Deyateli Rossii 1917 [Political Figures of Russia, 1917]*, In 227-228. Moskva: Nauchnoye Izdatel'stvo.
- Muhammedov, Ş. B. (2017). Uchebnoye Delo v Russkom Turkestane: V. P. Nalivkin i Tuzemniye Maktaby i Medrese, *Novaya i Noveyshaya İstoriya [Education in Russian Turkestan: V. P. Nalivkin and Indigenous Schools and Madrasas, Past and Recent History]*, (e-journal), 2017 (10):
<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/uchebnoe-delo-v-russkom-turkestane-v-p-nalivkin-i-tuzemnye-maktaby-i-medrese/viewer>, Access date: (30.07.2025).
- Nalivkin, Vladimir P. (2015). *Moi Vospominaniya o Skobelevе [My Memories of Skobelev]*. S. N. Abashin vd. (Ed.) *Polveka v Turkestane V. P. Nalivkin: Biografiya, Dokumentı, Trudı [V. P. Nalivkin in Turkestan: Half a Century of Life, Documents, and Works]*: In 525-553. Moskva: Izdatel'skii Dom Mardjani.
- Nalivkin, Vladimir P.-Maria Nalivkina, (2016). *Muslim Women of the Fergana Valley*. (Ed.) Mariana Markova-Marianne Kamp (Trans.) *Muslim Women of the Fergana Valley*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
- Nalivkin, Vladimir P. (1913). *Tuzemtsı Ranshe i Teper [The Natives Then and Now]*. Tashkent: Elektrich Tipolit. Turk.
- Shumakov, D. M. (2017). *Orlovskiy Bahtina Kadetskiy Korpus 1843-1918 [The Orlovsky Bakhtin Cadet Corps, 1843-1918]*. Yekaterinburg: Jitagent Ridero.
- Togan, Zeki V. (2020). *Hatıralar*. Ankara: Türkiye Diyanet Vakfı Yayınları.